

Challenges and Opportunities of Branding Agricultural Commodities: The Case of Rice Production in South Gondar Zone, Ethiopia

Dr. Kindye Essa

Asstt. Prof. , Dean, College of Business and Economics
Debre Tabor University- Ethiopia
<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-3554-8028>

Dr. Yissa Hassen

Department of Management, Faculty of Business and Economics,
Debre Tabor University, Debre Tabor, Ethiopia.
essahassen2009@gmail.com

Prof.(Dr.) Namita Rajput

Sri Aurobindo College ,University of Delhi ,
<https://orcid.org/0000-0001-7978-0959>

Prof. (Dr.) Bhupendra Kumar

Accounting & Finance, College of Business & Economics
Debre Tabor University Ethiopia
<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-9609-2311>

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Abstract

Agriculture is considered as one of the vital sector to sustain existence of people in the world. Branding in Agricultural commodities is at infant stage though it has too much contribution for the sellers and buyers. This paper is aimed at characterization and branding of rice harvested in South Gondar Zone. The study is explanatory with qualitative research approach which incorporates 185 Respondents from Model Farmers, Brokers, Merchant, Agriculture experts and Marketing expert. In order to collect data both primary and secondary sources were used. The primary data was collected through questionnaire, focus group discussion. Secondary data was also collected from CSA and other published sources. The study has employed descriptive statistics. The result of the study indicates that, the opportunities of branding of rice includes more efficient for standardized production process, it increases product protection against any harm, it is major determinant to buyer's choice, enhance customer loyalty, creates competition among brands, increase production, helps to meet international standards. In addition as the study revealed that place of origin branding and crowd branding was found useful for branding of rice produced in south Gondar zone. Based on the finding of the study, researchers

recommend rice production to be increased, and recommended place of origin branding and crowd branding to be used for branding of rice produced in south Gondar zone.

Key Words: Branding, Agricultural Commodity, Rice, Challenges, Opportunities

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1. Introduction

Agriculture is considered as one of the vital sectors to sustain the existence of people in the world. Agriculture has been Ethiopia's most important and dominant economic sector. According to Dawit (2015), Agriculture is the major source of livelihood to almost over 65% of the population of Ethiopia and it accounts for nearly 46% of GDP, 83% of employment, and nearly 80% of foreign export earnings.

According to Asmelash and Yemane, (2012) Ethiopia has been always known for producing diversified agricultural products and it has high potential for rice production. Rice is the staple food in which more than half of the world's population and at least 3.5 billion people are consuming (Takele, 2017). In the world, the largest volume of rice production is concentrated in countries China, India, and Indonesia with the percentage share of accounts for about 32.9, 24.4, and 11.0 % of the world production respectively Belayneh and Tekle, (2017). As per Belayneh and Tekle, (2017) Cultivation of rice in Ethiopia is generally a recent phenomenon it was started first at Fogera in the early 1970's and now it is grown at West central highlands of Amhara Region (Fogera, Gonder Zuria, Dembia, Takusa and Achefer); North West lowland areas of Amhara and Benshangul Regions (Jawi, Pawi, Metema and Dangur); Gamebilla regional state (Abobo and Etang Woredas) South and South West Lowlands of SNNP (Beralee, Weyito). In Ethiopia Branding of Agricultural products is not new and Ethiopia is known in its coffee and various brands of coffee like Yirgachaffee, Harar, Sidama, Limmu, jimma, Tepi, and Lekempti were accessed for national and international markets. In coffee branding one type of coffee is differentiated to another through Cleanliness, Acidity, Body, Flavour etc.

Since we are a country where a majority of our population lives in villages and is dependent on agriculture, we must fully utilize and promote this inherent strength towards enhancing the global reach and standing of Ethiopian agricultural produce along with other strategic moves for enhancing the income of our farmers. Good branding of agricultural products to be acceptable by the consumers across the globe and can enhance the income of the farmers. Several Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs) and cooperatives have recently been able to create brands of their products and services. However, Certification of products is very necessary as it can satisfy prescribed standards concerning origin, material, mode of manufacture, quality, accuracy and other characteristics. Few studies were conducted regarding Fogera rice. Although Mesfin and Zemedu (2015) have investigated production, marketing and biological constraints, challenges and opportunities of rice seed system in Fogera woreda to improve the seed marketing system of rice at household level and Tadesse, Solomon, and Fentahun, (2017) has investigated Analysis of technical efficiency of rice production in Fogera district of Ethiopia. But, none of the study focus on branding of rice produced in South Gondar.

For most of the rice products there is no remarkable perceived difference in the eyes of the consumers. The fact is that a market remains commodity driven if products fail to differentiate in the eyes of the consumer. Rice is perceived to be the same unless branded and therefore should command almost similar price. However, as commodity markets become more competitive, it leads to an increasing demand for branding of rice. Branding of rice needs to be extended beyond the basic product and successful differentiation should be based upon genuine differences. As a result, farmers,

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corporate sector and all related agencies with marketing of rice would recognize the fact that the future economic prosperity demands a paradigm shift from offering commodity in simple form to differentiated rice to the consumers.

One of the fundamental methods of differentiation involves branding of rice. The practice of Branding in Agricultural commodities is at infant stage though it has too much contribution for the sellers and buyers. There is also growing demand for rice products produced in South Gondar Zone. The researchers of this study are motivated to assess the challenges and opportunities of branding rice in South Gondar Zone.

2. Literature review

2.1. Definitions of brand and branding

The term Brand is defined by different scholars differently. As stated in Salokhe (2017), the word brand was derived from the word brand which means burn, the owners of live stoke were making small part of the animal skin burn to identity them easily. According to Shelly and Rajaram (2012), the practice of branding was started 5000 years ago in Mosopotamia that was relied on stone seals to differentiate on the caps and stoppers of oil and wine. Branding is the name, design or symbol that builds the foundation to differentiate the product and build foundation to protect trade mark (Kotler, Jain, Maesincee, 2002). The definition of a brand by Dibb (1997) and Kotler (2003) is almost similar in which they have defined the term brand as a name, term, sign, symbol, design, & accommodation that identities the goods and services of competitors. Branding helps people buy, identifies differences in products and services, gives buyers safety, offers the potential to build relationships with emotional connections, and enhances company value.

As per Zehir *etal* (2011), Brands are one of the most valuable intangible assets that companies in the consumer market should own. Though the term brand has an indication on the side of the sellers, according to Salokhe (2017), brand

represents what exists in the minds of consumers and not what the marketer intends to present through the brand in which a brand conveys certain attitude, perception or behaviour with the consumers' conscious or sub conscious to feel comfortable. .

2.2. Branding Strategies

Branding strategies vary based on target audience, nature of product, marketing campaigns and budgets. Branding strategies are the action plans that organizations use to differentiate their products, services, and identities from their competitors. Essentially, a brand strategy is a long-term strategy used to identify what kind of image you want to build for your customers. According to Zehir *etal*, (2011), Name brand recognition, Individual branding, Attitude Branding, Brand extension, Private labels and Crowd sourcing are the among the commonly used branding strategies. Zehir *etal*, (2011) have defined each types of branding strategies as Name brand recognition is using the company own name as a brand for its product and Usually companies use its logo, slogan, symbol, sound, color etc... as recognition. In addition, individual branding is using independent name for different products produced by parent company and it is applying easily recognizable brands for its unique identity products. On the other hand, Attitude Branding is bringing and using life personality and customized experience with products and service and it is also associating brand with certain style. Moreover, Brand extension also occurs when one of the company flagship brands Ventures in to a new market and it is applied when one company produces different types of products and the brand name carries its own identity to the product mix. A private label is a kind of branding which is used in supermarket and the company used cost effective brands to compete with large retailers. Crowd sourcing brands are outsourced to the public for brand creation, which allows customer and stakeholders the chance to be involved in the naming process, an effectively drives up personal interest in a product.

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According to Keller (1999), the branding strategies are classified as new product branding, Flanker branding, Brand line extension, and Brand leveraging. Keller (1999), has defined New product branding: as branding for a new product introduced to the market, Flanker branding is branding another brand in a category in which the firm already has, Brand line extension is using the companies brand name in the firms present product category, Brand leveraging (franchise extension) is the use of the existing brand name to enter a new product category is leveraging.

Docherty (2012), has identified the types of brand in toproducer brands, Varietal brands, Certification brand and Geographies brands. Docherty (2012) has defined producer brands as Distinguish between primary d/f product and producers, Varietal brands as distinguish b/n owners of d/t varieties of product of the variety, Geographies brands as distinguish products-regions through geographic origin association, and Certification brand as distinguish product through ethical or social standard.

2.3. Challenges and Opportunities of Branding

2.3.1. Challenges of Branding

Pajura (2017), has identified the challenges of branding as Difficult to create right name, slogan, and symbol for the product, it needs long term commitment, Addressing the consumer values, Scalability challenge, Market structure changes and Oatmeal name that did nothing/little about the company or product. Hayes and Lance (2015), has also identified the challenges of branding as financial constraint, lack of experts in marketing, lack of top management support, trust and lack of resource.

2.3.2. Opportunities of branding

Todor (2014), has identified that Brand is important to obtaining long term sustainable competitive advantage, a strong brand can add a share price from 5-7%, a brand strategy encourages positive consumer attitudes towards product, and brand leads to increase in

quality, competitive advantage through acceptable price and differentiation.

According to Kottler (2006), major benefits of a strong brand is to create customer recognition, competitive edge in market, easy introduction of new test of the product, customer loyalty and shared values, enhanced credibility and ease of purchase. According to Chiavravalle (2015), the economic benefits of creating a strong brand includes lowercost of sales, premium pricing, lower cost of promotion, and higher market share. Pajura (2017) has identified the benefits of branding for sellers and buyers separately. The benefits of branding for sellers include Earn high price, Lead brand loyalty, strong customer base, Differentiate the product, and Sense of pride. In addition, the benefits of branding for buyers include provide information about the product, assume better quality on brand products, and sense of pride.

According to Docherty (2012), Branding add value to the product by differentiating the product, convey additional information through launching and consumers perceive that branded products have better quality than unbranded. Brand is effective marketing strategy for agricultural product. For most of the agricultural products, there is no remarkable difference in the eyes of the consumer. If products fail to differentiate in the eyes of their consumers then the market remains commodity driven. Thus we can say that, for consumer, all variety of sugar, rice, wheat are perceived to be the same and therefore consumers may recommend almost similar price unless branded.

2.4. Branding of agricultural products

Singh (2016), states as there is no remarkable perceived difference in the agricultural products in the eyes of consumers. A commodity market becomes more competitive and price is also depressed this leads to increasing demand for branding. Singh (2016) has identified the opportunity of agricultural branding in terms of size trend and geographical location, identity the values added to the technology, scale and production and commercial expertise, disclose

the values proposition to consumer that need to be discussed before branding of agricultural products. Pajure (2017), stated that farmers can enhance their income if they start branding their commodities.

Ngozi (2012) in his thesis work, stated that branding strategy is considered as an accepted part of marketing activity and a norm in manufacturing & processed food products. Many agricultural products are unbranded since agricultural products do not have clear brand, it is common to use generic brand associated with group of suppliers. Farmers sell their products as commodities. In order to within agricultural marketing of completion branding strategy is crucial. Lack of branding in agricultural product reduces the farmer's income and adequate protection of consumer. Packaging is a marketing tool used to reflect the brand. White and Zwart (1996), Agricultural commodities have their own variety in a product line due to climate, environmental and management difference, environmental and management difference and biological growing process.

As per Singh (2016), branding of agricultural products is successful when it can add differentiation rather than giving name, and it has to offer reputation and preference on consumer by creating real value. Chiavravalle (2015), giving name for agricultural products is not the only solution to enhance income of farmers because it is difficult to differentiate agricultural products in the eye of customers. But Singh (2016), stated that branding of agricultural products help farmers and other value chain actors to achieve security of the product and obtain modern farming and marketing techniques that increase productivity and leads to path of self-sufficiency.

Branding of Rice

The size of rice grain ranges into long, medium and short varieties and ranges from fluffy to creamy to sticky in texture. Color varies from brown to white to red. The shape, size, texture and other characteristics of the different varieties affect the way the rice is used in recipes, what types of dish it is suitable for, and

the way it is cooked. In the world today, there are lots of branded rice and Basmati rice, Chinese black rice, Glutinous rice, Jasmine rice and Paella rice are known in its brand (Hensperger and Kaufmann. 2003).

Eriko Miyagawe (2018), Branding of rice is important not only for producers to differentiate one product to another it is also necessary for consumers since consumer need to differentiate how one variety is delicious and functionality and qualitative of rice is also varied. White and Zwart (1996), stated that agricultural products have high level of product variety the product attribute. Hence brand can be relied on making difference various attributes either during or post production attributes. Consumer will pay high for branded product. Branding reduces consumers time and cost to differentiate one product to the other. Country of origin is used to identity agricultural products and it could be applied in rice.

3. Research Methodology

3.1. Research design

According to Gravetter and Foranzo (2011), Research design can be explanatory (descriptive). Descriptive research investigates and describes the characteristics of the variables, and its aim is to describe characteristics and functions. Descriptive research is more concerned with what happened rather than how or why something has happened. As a result in order to identify the challenges and opportunities of branding rice produced in south Gondar zone Descriptive research design was employed.

3.2. Research Approach

The research approach is categorized in to qualitative, quantitative and mixed method. Qualitative research is an approach for exploring and understanding the meaning individuals or groups ascribe to a social or human problem. Quantitative research is an approach for testing objective theories by examining the relationship among variables. Mixed methods research is an approach to inquiry involving collecting both quantitative and qualitative data, integrating the two forms

(Creswell, 2014). In this study qualitative data was employed as the nature of data is identifying the challenges and opportunities.

3.3. Sources of Data

Sekaran and Bougie (2016), has categorized the sources of data in to primary and secondary sources. They have defined primary source as the as the original source of data in which the data was collected for the first time to meet the specific purpose. On the other hand, they have defined secondary source of data as source of data that has been used by other party for another purpose than the current study but still it can be used for the current study. In this study, the researchers have used primary source of data. The primary data were collected from sample respondents.

3.4. Data collection tools

Data collection instruments are tools used for data collection. Among the different primary data collection instruments, the researchers have employed questionnaire, and physical measurement (laboratory experiment). The researchers have collected information using questionnaire from Farmers, merchants, agriculture, marketing experts) In addition, 1 sample was selected from each category of respondents and a total of 20 Focus discussion participants were selected and focus group discussion was conducted based on the raised questions.

3.5. Population

Sekaran and Bougie (2016), defined Population as the pool of people from which research participants are drawn. Population is the full universe of people or things from which the samples were selected. The population of this research are farmers, farmer Union members, merchants, and agriculture and marketing experts who are involved in rice production and found in Amhara region.

3.6. Sampling and sample size

In this study multi stage sampling were used. In this study multistage sampling; cluster sampling followed by proportional stratified sampling. From different zones of Amhara region, areas which produce rice were selected using cluster sampling and are farmers, model farmer, merchants, and agriculture and marketing experts were selected using proportional stratified sampling. According to Belayneh and tekle, (2017) rice grow in many parts of the region, the predominant potential areas are Fogera, Dera, Farta, and Libo kemkem etc...). As a result, in the study Fogera, Dera, Farta, and Libo kemkem woreda were selected as a sample area and rice produced from each areas were selected. In addition, the following samples were selected using disproportional stratified sampling from each selected Woredas.

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Samples from each population	Fogera	Dera	Farta	Libokemkem	Total sample
Farmers	35	35	35	35	140
Merchants	10	10	10	10	40
Brokers	2	2	2	2	8
Agriculture experts	2	2	2	2	8
Marketing experts	1	1	1	1	4
Total	50	50	50	50	200

In order to determine the representative sample size, Krejci, Dan and Morgan (1970), sample size determination techniques and Yamane (1967), sample size formula which is shown below were used assuming a 95% confidence level and e = 0.5 precision.

$$n = \frac{N}{1 + N(e)^2}$$

Where, n = sample size

N= Population size of each variable

3.7. Data Analysis

Data are something we collect and analyse and provides information in order to arrive at research conclusions. Data analysis refers to the systematic organization and synthesis of research data and testing research hypothesis. The two available methods of data analysis in survey research design are descriptive and inferential statistics. Descriptive statistics are used to describe the data collected in research studies and to accurately characterize the variables under observation within a specific sample. Descriptive statistics enable us to obtain an overall image of the research data

3.9. Reliability

e = level of precision

and assist by presenting the data in a user-friendly and orderly way (Sekaran and Bougie 2016). As a result, in this research Descriptive analysis was computed to identify challenges and opportunities of branding rice.

3.8. Validity

Validity indicates a degree to which a test, measurement and instrument is capable of achieving certain aims. In order to test the strength of questionnaires, the researcher has given the first draft of the instruments to the experts. In doing so, some improvements were made thoroughly.

Table 3.9-1: Reliability Test of Instruments

Questions Category	Cronbach's Alpha	No of Items
Practice of rice branding of Rice	0.837	12
Opportunity of Branding	0.786	15
Challenges of Branding	0.856	10

3.16. Opportunities and Challenges of Branding in South Gondar Zone

S.No	Raised Questions (Opportunity of Branding)	Responses	Frequency	Percentage	Rank
1	More efficient for standardized production process	No	19	10.3%	1
		Yes	166	89.7%	
2	It increases product protection against any harm	No	20	10.8%	2
		Yes	165	89.2%	
3	It is major determinant to buyer's choice	No	22	11.4%	3
		Yes	164	88.6%	
4	Enhance customer loyalty	No	23	12.4%	4
		Yes	162	87.6%	
5	Creates competition among brands	No	24	13.0%	5
		Yes	161	87.0%	
6	Increase production	No	26	14.1%	6
		Yes	159	85.9%	
7	Helps to meet international standards	No	28	15.1%	7
		Yes	157	84.9%	
8	Helps in consumers choice decision	No	35	18.9%	

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		Yes	150	81.1%	8
9	It is appropriate market entry strategy for agricultural marketers	No	39	21%	9
		Yes	146	79%	
10	Ensures product quality	No	42	22.7%	10
		Yes	143	77.3%	
11	Increase ability to serve separate markets with separate products	No	44	23.8%	11
		Yes	141	76.2%	
12	Customers pay more money for branded products	No	51	27.6%	12
		Yes	134	72.4%	
13	Differentiate among brands	No	54	29.2%	13
		Yes	131	70.8%	
14	Reduces overall sales costs	No	87	47.0%	14
		Yes	98	53.0%	
15	It makes easier to match products to the customer's needs	No	98	53.0%	15
		Yes	87	47.0%	

Source: Own Survey, 2021

Opportunities of branding of rice

For the purpose of identifying the opportunities of branding of rice instruments were adopted and the results of the study were identified. Table 4.2.7 shows the results of the opportunities of branding of rice for the farmers, merchants, brokers and other stakeholders. In order to rank the opportunities of branding of rice, the percentage and maximum frequency of answers respondents were used.

The result of the study indicates that, the rank of opportunities of branding of rice which accounts 166 (89.7%), more efficient for standardized production process, 165 (89.2%) it increases product protection against any harm, 164 (88.6%) it is major determinant to buyer's choice, 162 (87.6%) enhance customer loyalty,

161 (87%) creates competition among brands, 159 (86%) Increase production, 157 (85%) helps to meet international standards, 150 (81%) helps in consumers' choice decision, 146 (79%) it is appropriate market entry strategy for agricultural marketers, 143 (77%) ensures product quality, 141(76%) increase ability to serve separate markets with separate products, 134 (72%) customers pay more money for branded products, 131 (71%) differentiate among brands, 98 (53%) reduces overall sales costs, and 87 (47%) it makes easier to match products to the customer's needs. As a result, it can be inferred that almost more than half of the respondents shows an agreement with advantages of branding or rice as previous researchers has identified.

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Challenges of Branding of Rice

S.No	Raised Questions (Challenges of Branding)	Responses	Frequency	Percentage	Rank
1	It needs long term commitment	No	18	9.7%	1
		Yes	167	90.3%	
2	Standardization of agricultural product is impossible	No	27	14.6%	2
		Yes	158	85.4%	
3	It is difficult to have right brand	No	31	16.2%	3
		Yes	154	83.2%	
4	Consumers do not want branded product	No	36	19.5%	4
		Yes	149	80.5%	

5	It is difficult to control brand since rice has many producers	No	44	23.8%	5
		Yes	141	76.2%	
6	Failure to constantly upgrade brand image	No	54	29.8%	6
		Yes	131	70.2%	
7	Addressing the consumers value is challenging	No	77	41.6%	7
		Yes	108	58.4%	
8	High Pressure to compete on price	No	87	47.0%	8
		Yes	98	53.0%	
9	Difficulty in owning brand since there are many producers	No	95	51.4%	9
		Yes	90	48.6%	
10	Competing globally with local brand is difficult	No	105	56.8%	10
		Yes	80	43.2%	

Source: Own Survey, 2021

Challenges of branding of rice

For the purpose of identifying the Challenges of branding of rice instruments were adopted and the results of the study were identified. Table 4.2.8 shows the results of the challenges of branding of rice for the farmers, merchants, brokers and other stakeholders. In order to rank the opportunities of branding of rice, the percentage and maximum frequency of answers respondents were used.

The result of the study indicates that, the rank of challenges of branding of rice which accounts 167 (90%) it needs long term commitment, 158 (85.4%) i Standardization of agricultural product is impossible, 154 (83%) it is difficult to have right brand, 149 (80.5%) Consumers do not want branded product, 141 (76.2%) it is difficult to control brand since rice has many producers, 131 (70.2%) failure to constantly upgrade brand image, 108 (58.4%) addressing the consumers value is challenging, 98 (53.0%) high Pressure to compete on price, 90 (48.6%) difficulty in owning brand since there are many producers, 80 (43.2%) competing globally with local brand is difficult. As a result, it can be inferred that almost more than half of the respondents shows an agreement with advantages of branding or rice as previous researchers has identified.

Analysis of the Focus Group discussion

Focus group discussion instruments were prepared to get information in order to brand

rice produced in south Gondar Zone. For the Focus Group discussion 20 respondents were selected and all have attended the focus group discussion. The respondents were from Libo kemkem, Dera, Fogera and Farta woredas. The participants of focus group discussion were Farmers, Merchants, Brokers, Agriculture experts and Marketing experts which were selected from stated woredas. The Focus Group Discussion was held in Woreta town. And the researchers were act as facilitator for the focus group discussion.

The first question rose for respondents were whether they know what branding is? And most of the respondents replied that branding is a means to differentiate one's own product to the other. And they associate brand with quality of commodities like cloth, technology equipment and cosmetics items.

The second question rose for respondents were Do agricultural products in Ethiopia branded? And almost all respondents replied negative response as branding of agricultural commodity is not common in Ethiopia. But, in mid of the discussion one of the participant raised the case of coffee and respondents has stated many brands of coffee like Jimma Coffe, Harrar Coffee, siidama coffee and yigrachefe coffee. In addition, ideas was raised from another participant that seyite teff is also another brand name for teff product produced in Amhara

region. Hence branding of agricultural products is possible.

The third important question rose during the focus group discussion was Do you think branding of rice produced in south Gondar zone is important? And respondents have raised different idea. They have mentioned the benefit of branding of rice to have a differentiation of locally produced rice with imported rice. In addition, branding of rice helps the farmers, merchants and brokers to sell their product in regional and national markets. If the rice product produced in south Gondar zone is branded, it will help farmers to sell their products easily and to get protection of their product against any harm. Participants of the focus group discussion have also stated as branding of rice will help to compete in national market and to create awareness about the benefits of rice and for what kind of food could it be useful.

The fourth question rose during the focus group discussion was to what extent does branding enhance the marketing of agricultural products? And the benefits of branding for farmers, merchants and brokers include earning high return, lead brand preference, create strong customer base, differentiate the product from imported and other products, and create sense of pride. In addition, the branding of rice cultivated in south Gondar zone will help for buyers and consumers by providing information about the product, and assume better quality on brand products.

Another important question rose was regarding the bases for differentiating rice products? And respondents were supposed to elaborate the Physical and Biological characteristic that helps to differentiate one rice variety to the other. And the respondent's stated that there are lots of rice varieties in south Gondar zone and the productivity and the suitable climate of each Variety is different. As per the participant's feedback, Physical characteristics include colour, size, shape place of origin etc... is used as a base to differentiate while the biological characteristics like includes the nutritional

values, water moisture, and chemical composition. Some of the rice varieties are white in colour while others are reddish. The colour of rise can be easily detected even before milled. The reddish colour is somehow longer than the white one. In addition, the productivity of rice varies as per the harvesting treatment, water consumption during harvesting, and the fertilizer consumed during harvesting. Rice products which need drier and mostly moistures are different in nature and productivity. The agriculture experts have clearly identified the difference interms of nutritional values depending on the previous studied conducted in rice varieties produced in south Gobdar zone the x- jigna enget, Shaga, Fogera, Adet and others bases on protein, fat, fiber, carbohydrate and minerals bases on laboratory test.

The sixth important question rose was regarding the types of branding and which branding techniques is appropriate for branding of rice produced in South Gondar Zone? The facilitator of the focus group discussion has identified and elaborated about the meanings of place of origin branding, flanker branding, brand leveraging, crowd branding and private branding. During the initial discussion participants agree about the appropriateness of place of origin branding and crowd branding to be used for branding of rice produced in south Gondar zone. The participates recommend place of origin branding to be used since the rice products are harvested in south Gondar zone different woredas and they have raised the branding techniques used by coffee harvesters and marketers in Ethiopia. In addition, participants propose crowd branding to be applied for branding of rive produced in South Gondar Zone. Crowd branding is a technique of branding in which the public is supposed to give brand name for products and agree to use the most consensus brand name.

The last question raised for respondents was to propose the brand name for rice products produced in south Gondar zone. For this question many ideas were raised including the

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use of private branding to use the rice variety name as a brand name. In addition, using place of origin branding to be used as a brand name in which there will be lots of name for one variety of brands since it is harvested in different areas. Moreover, the farmers' cooperative was also proposed to be the one to call brand name for rice products. The use of collective name to use Fogera Rice was also proposed by many participants though it has complains by some participants. Hence, from the mostly stated responses of respondents the researchers claim that using Crowd branding and place of origin branding would be more appropriate and the participation of stakeholders is essential.

5.1. Conclusions

- From the survey respondents it can be inferred that most of the respondents were farmers and the rest respondents have covered the concerned parties from Merchants, brokers, agriculture experts and marketing experts in South Gondar Zone.
- The result of the study indicates that, the opportunities of branding of rice includes more efficient for standardized production process, it increases product protection against any harm, it is major determinant to buyer's choice, enhance customer loyalty, creates competition among brands, increase production, helps to meet international standards, helps in consumers' choice decision, it is appropriate market entry strategy for agricultural marketers, ensures product quality, increase ability to serve separate markets with separate products, customers pay more money for branded products, differentiate among brands, reduces overall sales costs, and it makes easier to match products to the customer's needs.
- The result of the study indicates that, the rank of challenges of branding of rice which accounts it needs long term commitment, standardization of agricultural product is impossible, it is difficult to have right brand, consumers do not want branded product, it is difficult to control brand since rice has many

producers, failure to constantly upgrade brand image, addressing the consumers value is challenging, high Pressure to compete on price, difficulty in owning brand since there are many producers, and competing globally with local brand is difficult.

- Participants of focus group discussion agree about the appropriateness of place of origin branding and crowd branding to be used for branding of rice produced in south Gondar zone. Hence, from the mostly stated responses of respondents the researchers claim that using Crowd branding and place of origin branding would be more appropriate and the participation of stakeholders is essential.

5.2. Recommendations

Based on the finding of the study the following recommendations are forwarded.

The farmers and harvesters who are engaged in rice production shall increase production of rice since there is growing demand of rice product in the country even the import of rice is increasing from time to time. In addition, the researchers recommend rice to be harvested in new areas (Woredas) which are conducive for rice product. Although branding of rice has challenges as the practice of agricultural commodity branding is infant, Branding of rice is very important for farmers, merchants, brokers and other stakeholders to increase the buyer's choice, enhance customer loyalty, creates competition among brands, increase production, helps to meet international standards. Hence, researchers recommend rice produced in south Gondar zone should be branded and it should have brand owner.

In addition, Participants of focus group discussion agree about the appropriateness of place of origin branding and crowd branding to be used for branding of rice produced in south Gondar zone. Hence, from the mostly stated responses of respondents the researchers recommend that using Crowd branding and place of origin branding would be more appropriate and the participation of stakeholders is essential. For this stage researchers recommend Fogera rice to be the

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proposed brand name to be used for rice products produced in South Goondar zone region temporarily since most of the rice produced in sough Gondar zone accounts for Fogera area..

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